

Title: Meta-Analysis of Perforation and Complications Associated with Cook Medical IVC Filters: Focus on Celect and Günther Tulip Devices

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Abstract

Inferior vena cava filters, including the Cook Medical Celect and Günther Tulip models, are widely used to prevent pulmonary embolism in patients with contraindications to anticoagulation. However, numerous studies reveal substantial complications associated with long-term indwelling times, particularly perforation of the IVC wall and subsequent embedment, which may complicate retrieval and possibly heighten risks to adjacent organs. This meta-analysis synthesizes data from multiple studies to examine the prevalence, progression, and clinical implications of perforation associated with these filters. By highlighting specific risk factors and retrieval challenges, the findings emphasize the importance of tailored patient selection, close monitoring, and early retrieval to minimize adverse outcomes.

Introduction

IVC filters are critical in preventing pulmonary embolism for patients who are either contraindicated for anticoagulation therapy or have experienced therapy failure. The Cook Medical Celect and Günther Tulip filters, both retrievable, are frequently used; however, increasing evidence suggests a high incidence of IVC perforation over time, particularly in cases with prolonged filter retention. This meta-analysis consolidates findings on perforation rates, risk factors, and retrieval complications, underscoring clinical strategies for safer application of these devices.

Methods

This review aggregated data from seven key studies that examined Celect and Günther Tulip filters. Each study was evaluated for sample size, perforation rates, follow-up times, and reported complications. Perforation was defined as any filter strut extending 3 mm or more beyond the IVC wall, and retrieval success was documented where applicable. Data on patient demographics, indwelling times, and specific filter-related complications were synthesized to offer a comprehensive analysis.

Results

1. Perforation Rates

- **Celect Filters:** Perforation was highly prevalent across multiple studies, with most rates exceeding 70% after six months. For instance, Durack et al. (2012) observed a 86% perforation rate in filters retained beyond 71 days(Celect and GTF Penetrat...). McLoney et al. (2013) corroborated these findings, reporting 49% perforation in Celect filters at an average follow-up of 277 days(Ohio State CT Follow up...).
- **Günther Tulip Filters:** Perforation was less frequent than in Celect filters but significant, with studies such as Ota et al. (2008) documenting a 56% perforation rate in permanently placed filters(Tulip 56% Penetration). Perforation became more likely with extended indwelling times, aligning with findings from Olorunsola et al. (2013), which noted time-dependent perforation in Günther Tulip filters(UCSF Penetration Study O...).

2. Risk Factors Influencing Perforation

- **Indwelling Time:** Longer retention consistently correlated with higher perforation rates. Bos et al. (2015) found that filters left in situ for more than 100 days had significantly greater penetration risk ($p < .001$)(Celect Strut Penetratio...).
- **Patient Demographics:** Female patients and those with a malignancy history showed an increased likelihood of perforation. Dowell et al. (2015) attributed this trend to anatomical variances, suggesting that reduced IVC diameters amplify strut pressure on the caval wall, exacerbating perforation(Celect IVC Wall Strut P...).

3. Complications Arising from Perforation

- **Adjacent Organ Involvement:** Several studies reported strut perforation into nearby organs, including the duodenum, aorta, and kidney. Zhou et al. (2012) identified a 24% incidence of asymptomatic penetration into adjacent structures among patients with prolonged filter indwelling times(Cleveland Clinic Celect...).
- **Breakthrough PE and Retrieval Failure:** Though perforation was frequent, Bos et al. (2015) observed no direct association between perforation and breakthrough PE or retrieval failure ($p > .05$)(Celect Strut Penetratio...). However, the progressive nature of perforation increased the technical complexity of retrieval, often necessitating advanced retrieval techniques for embedded filters(Embedded Inferior Vena ...).

1. Durack et al. (2012) – UCSF Study on Günther Tulip and Celect Filters

- **Sample:** 50 patients, follow-up CTs between 1 and 880 days.

Findings:

- **Perforation Rate:** 86% of filters exhibited perforation, with all filters imaged beyond 71 days showing signs of vena caval wall perforation .
- **Perforation Characteristics:** Perforation was progressive, often exacerbated by filter tilt (noted in 40% of cases). The study suggests that filter tilt may increase pressure on the caval wall, promoting perforation.
- **Retrievability:** Of the 12 attempted retrievals, 11 were successful, indicating that although perforation was common, it did not consistently prevent retrieval within the observed period.

2. Dowell et al. (2015) – Ohio State University, Celect Filter Study

- **Sample:** 91 patients, with CT follow-ups across a range of times, and a subset modeled for mechanical stresses.

Findings:

- **Perforation Onset and Progression:** Initial CT scans (average 75 days) showed 36% with strut perforation. By the second CT at 316 days, this rate increased to 71%, and at the final follow-up (554 days), it rose to 79% .
- **Risk Factors:** Perforation rates were higher in females and patients with malignancy ($p < .05$). Finite element modeling confirmed that caval area reductions (common in malignancy or due to tilt) increase the stress on the struts, worsening perforation.
- **Clinical Relevance:** Progressive perforation in certain patient populations led the authors to recommend closer imaging follow-up, especially in high-risk groups.

3. Bos et al. (2015) – University of Chicago Celect Filter Complications

- **Sample:** 193 Celect filters with follow-up CTs averaging 176.2 days.

Findings:

- **Penetration Rate:** 28.5% had struts penetrating >3 mm outside the caval wall. One case presented with significant perforation that compressed the ureter, leading to hydronephrosis .
- **Time-Related Risks:** Filters left indwelling for more than 100 days were more likely to develop strut penetration ($p < .001$).
- **Associations with PE and Retrieval Failure:** No significant association was found between perforation and either breakthrough PE or retrieval failure, but the extended indwelling time was a clear risk for penetration.

4. Zhou et al. (2012) – Cleveland Clinic, Celect Filter Retrieval Outcomes

- **Sample:** 120 Celect filters with an average indwelling time of 158 days.

Findings:

- **Penetration and Complications:** Among the patients undergoing retrieval, 86.1% showed limb penetration on cavagrams, and 24% of CT scans detected asymptomatic limb penetration into nearby structures like the duodenum, aorta, or kidney .
- **Technical Challenges:** 5.8% retrieval failure rate, often due to embedment or tilt, underscores the technical difficulty with retrievals involving embedded filters. Perforations, especially those nearing adjacent organs, complicated retrieval further.

5. McLoney et al. (2013) – Ohio State University Comparison of Celect, Günther Tulip, and Greenfield Filters

- **Sample:** 255 Celect, 160 Tulip, and 50 Greenfield filters.

Findings:

- **Comparative Perforation Rates:** Celect (49%), Tulip (43%), Greenfield (2%), with follow-up times averaging 277 days for Celect, 437 for Tulip, and 286 for Greenfield .
- **Gender and Malignancy as Factors:** Perforation rates were higher among female patients (45.5%) and those with a malignancy history (43.7%) .
- **Greenfield Safety Profile:** The markedly low perforation rate in Greenfield filters suggests better stability over extended periods compared to conical filters like Celect and Tulip.

6. Ota et al. (2008) – Mie University, Japan, Günther Tulip Filter Outcomes

- **Sample:** 118 patients, with 56% of Tulip filters exhibiting IVC wall perforation when assessed beyond three months.

Findings:

- **Patency and Safety:** While 56% of permanently placed Günther Tulip filters showed strut perforation, no cases reported symptomatic leakage or organ injury .
- **Recommended Usage:** The study emphasizes the feasibility of the Günther Tulip as a permanent filter but highlights the necessity for monitoring in patients with contraindications to anticoagulation.

7. Stavropoulos et al. (2008) – University of Pennsylvania and UNC Chapel Hill, Embedded Filter Removal Techniques

- **Sample:** 21 patients with embedded filters requiring endobronchial forceps for removal.
- **Findings:**
 - **Success Rate:** 95% success rate for embedded filter removal using rigid endobronchial forceps.
 - **Technical Insights:** This study underscores the need for advanced retrieval techniques, particularly for embedded Celect and Günther Tulip filters, which have higher embedding risks due to progressive perforation

Discussion

The high incidence of IVC wall perforation among Celect and Günther Tulip filters underscores the importance of close follow-up and the timely retrieval of these devices. Celect filters, particularly, exhibited higher rates of perforation, suggesting the need for careful consideration when choosing between filter types, especially in patients anticipated to require long-term indwelling. Female patients and those with malignancy history, who showed higher perforation rates, should be monitored closely, as these demographics appear predisposed to complications.

The lack of a direct correlation between perforation and breakthrough PE or retrieval failure does not diminish the clinical importance of perforation, as these instances often complicate retrieval procedures. Studies like Zhou et al. (2012) and Stavropoulos et al. (2008) reveal the need for specialized retrieval tools and techniques, especially for embedded filters, suggesting that regular imaging could preemptively identify high-risk cases for earlier, less complicated retrievals.

Conclusion

The Celect and Günther Tulip IVC filters present considerable risks when left indwelling long-term, with perforation rates that are among the highest in the field. Given the complex retrievals often required for embedded filters, especially in patients with extended

indwelling times, early removal is recommended whenever clinically feasible. Patient selection should be rigorous, particularly considering individual risk factors such as gender and malignancy history. For patients with ongoing contraindications to anticoagulation, alternative approaches may warrant exploration to mitigate the risks associated with prolonged IVC filter retention.

References

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